

Lived Experiences of Drop-out Children: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

Christian E. Amagan

Northern Negros State College of Science and Technology, Negros Occidental, Philippines
ChristianAmagan@yahoo.com

Abstract – *This study was conducted to describe and analyze the lived experiences of the drop-out children. The respondents of the study are the actual drop-out of Laga-an Elementary School. It is a qualitative study which is a phenomenology in nature since it sought to explore reasons on drop-out phenomena. Using an interview guide with close and open ended questions, the researcher was able to interview four respondents which in fact a strong foundation to assure that the data is reliable since it allows the researcher to explore their individual experiences for data saturation. The respondents were interviewed twice. The researcher likewise conducted focus group discussion for triangulation of data. The data gathered from the respondents were translated and coded to as general meanings, out of the general meanings gathered, the researcher determined responses which are relevant to the phenomena, the relevant meanings were then clustered, and the clustered relevant meaning were then grouped to form necessary themes which answers the researchers purpose on the conduct of this study. On the process, the researcher was able to generate seven essential themes namely: child work; child labor; relevance of education to life; parents' financial stability and literacy; malnutrition; lack of interest or motivation; and school related problems. Drop out phenomena is also attributed with problems related to school. Hence, school must also acknowledge that partly, they have contributed to the phenomena.*

Keywords – *Drop-outs, Live Experiences, Phenomenology*

INTRODUCTION

“Nothing fortuitous happens in a child's world. There are no accidents. Everything is connected with everything else and everything can be explained by everything else”

School dropout is a very complex phenomenon, a very dangerous one, due to the fact that it happens much too easily and frequently. It has been confirmed that there is a strong connection between the family environment and the rate of school dropout. The family-related factors (standards of living, parent-child relationship, models of parenting) represent the main causes for school dropout (Gabriela Chirteş, 2010).

In legal concept about education, it is clearly stated in Article XIV Sec. 1 of 1987 Philippine Constitution, the state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all. Hence, every Filipino has the right to

an education which is commensurate to his/her own abilities and chosen field and it is not a chance nor a privilege. However, several Filipinos specially children are not acquainted and somehow forgotten the significance of this right. As a matter of fact, several educational institutions had reported pupils dropped out from schooling. Moreover, the national statistics had reported that at present, dropout rate remains at its

constant percentage (from 1 to 2 %) in every school level.

The government itself had implemented programs and policies to minimize and address the problem, many researchers had invested time to determine factors on the cause of this phenomena. However, still up to this present, it is a continuing struggle on educational departments. This inspires the researcher to conduct a study not just to determine factors but to describe and analyze reasons related to the phenomena of dropping out of school children through in depth exploration of their lived experiences.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims to describe and analyze the lived experiences of dropout children and the reasons attributed to incidence of dropping out of children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilized qualitative research using phenomenology as an approach. Qualitative research is primarily exploratory research. It is used to uncover trends in thought and opinions, and dive deeper into the problem (Wyse, 2011). Furthermore, it is exploring the issues, understanding the phenomena, and answering questions by analyzing and making sense of structured data (QSR, International, 2014).

Phenomenology, as applied to research, is the study of phenomena: their nature and meanings (Finlay, 2009; as cited by Kafle, 2011). Likewise, it describes the meaning of experiences lived by several individuals and seeks to understand the essence of those experiences (Hatch 2002, as cited by Tuttle 2012).

For this study, descriptive phenomenology was used since its primary purpose was to provide a thorough description and analysis of the lived experiences of drop out children and to elicit reasons attributed to their decision of dropping out from schooling.

The phenomenological method in human science recommends that one uses at least three participants (Giorgi, 2009; and cited by Englander, 2012). In addition, Boyd (2001) and as cited by Groenewald (2004) regards two to ten participants or research subjects as sufficient to research saturation. Hence, four conversation partners were utilized in this study.

In identifying the conversation partners, purposive sampling was used in which, it is an intentional selection of respondents based on their ability to elucidate a specific theme, concept or phenomena. Respondents must be an actual drop out of the school on previous school years or at present.

Since, the respondents were considered minors, the consent of their parents were sought through a duly signed parents' consent. The real names of the respondents were considered confidential; thus the research utilizes different names as their code.

The instrument utilized in this study was questionnaires with open ended questions used as interview guides specifically prepared for the chosen respondents. The researcher believes that the use of this instrument is appropriate to both respondents since it caters responses which are relevant and useful for the purpose and objective of this study. Likewise, Van Manen (1990) as cited by Schumacher (2012) states that formulating good questions before interview is essential to ensure quality throughout the interview. Thus, the interview guide used has one main overarching question and some specific questions to encourage the respondents to relay a rich description of their individual experiences.

The utilized interview guide underwent a content validity from 5 validators to determine the relevance of questions to the purpose or objective of this study.

The researcher also made use of recording gadgets to record conversation with the respondents and to ensure the accuracy of the data.

Cuelo (2012) emphasizes that in phenomenology, the optimum way of collecting data is through one-to-one interviews.

Englander (2012) likewise stated that the interview has become the main data collection procedure closely associated with qualitative, human scientific research. Further, phenomenological researches tend to choose the interview due to their interest in the meaning of phenomenon as it is lived by other subjects.

Hence, in line with the above statements, to elicit the data needed for the study, and to capture the richness of the lived experiences of drop out children, the researcher utilized a semi-structured interview.

At first, the researcher sent a letter to the principal asking for reported list of drop out children of the school from previous school years or at present. Upon the immediate response of the school principal, the researcher had identified the four conversation partners that were an actual dropout of the school and whose presence and residence were available and accessible. The researcher then had personally met the respondents and explained the purpose and importance of their participation in the study.

The collection of data started after the researcher had secured the parental consent of the child.

Researcher recommend completing an informed consent form immediately after establishing the research procedures, but before data collection begins (Rudestam and Newton, 2011; and cited by Zeeck, 2012)

The schedule of the interview was set at the most convenient time and date of the conversation partners. It was conducted in a private setting of the interviewee's choice. The researcher had rest assured that the respondents responses will be kept confidentially, ensuring that it will be used for the purpose of this study.

The interview was conducted using the dialect of the conversation partners to encourage them to precisely and richly describe their experiences of the phenomenon being studied. According to Benner (1994) and cited by Healy (2012), communicative context must prevent the participants from feeling awkward or constrained by the interview process by the use of foreign or abstract language.

Each respondent was interviewed twice which is supported by Seidman (1991) and Benner (1994) and cited by Healy (2012), both advocate interviewing participants two to three times, as it promotes understanding through clarifying initial interpretations and allowing for crucial questions to be asked which may overlook in previous interviews.

Likewise, each of the interviews was audio-recorded using mobile phone.

On the first interview, the researcher assured that the respondent is at ease and comfortable, reminding that they have the right to end the conversation anytime they want and their responses will be audio-recorded. Interview started using the interview guide translated into Sinugbuanong Binisaya.

On an interval of three days, the second interview was conducted. This was designed to make follow-up questions on the transcribed statements of the conversation partners that need clarifications and elaborations.

After the respondents were interviewed, they were subjected to focus group discussion for triangulation of data to emphasize validity. Triangulation has been viewed as a qualitative strategy to test validity through the convergence of information from different sources (Carter et al., 2014).

The researcher made the decision to end the data collection when data saturation had been reached. This was supported by Siege (2002) which stipulates that the data saturation occurs when the researcher is no longer hearing or seeing new information. Similarly, Saumure and Given (2008) defines data saturation as the point that new data emerge. Further, Tay (2014) emphasizes that the current accepted definition of data saturation is not that data collection has to conclude because of resource limitations but that no new insights have been observed.

The researcher used Grounded theory which both described (Husserlian) and analyzed (Heideger) the phenomena.

Particularly, interview data were explicated using simplified version of Hycner's (1999) explication process used by Groenewald (2004) and Calimpong (2014). Data explication was done richly to describe the essence of live experiences of dropout children. This explication process involves five steps that were partially followed by the researcher. The fifth steps were already integrated to the third and fourth steps, that is, the determination of the general and unique themes for all the interviews. When the units of the relevant meanings were clustered and forms into themes, all the interviews were considered.

The procedure of data explication that were observe are as follows:

1. Bracketing and phenomenological reduction. During this phase, the researcher repeatedly listens to the audio recording of each interview to become familiar with the words of the interviewee in order to develop a holistic sense, the "gestalt", as recommended by Holloway (1997) and Hycner (1999) and cited by Groenewald (2004). At this point, the researcher

entered the word of the respondents and absorbed the uniqueness of their experiences.

2. Delineating units of meaning. At this phase, the researcher examined the units of general meanings. Then, these meanings were carefully determined whether the statements of the respondents answered and illuminated the research questions. If the statements appeared to address the phenomenon being studied, then it is categorized as a unit of relevant meanings; on the other hand, irrelevant statements are discarded. Further, clearly redundant units are eliminated (Moustakas, 1999; and cited by Groenewald). Units of relevant meanings were presented in Appendix H.

3. Clustering of units of meaning to form themes. In this phase, the units identified as relevant were carefully scrutinized and grouped together according to essence they encompass forming clusters (Appendix I). Sadala and Adorno (2001) And as cited by Groenewald (2004) call this cluster of themes as significant topics or units of significance.

Then, the researcher thoroughly examined the clusters of units of relevant meanings to determine the central themes conveyed by the essence of the cluster and determine the number of themes that are attributes on the reasons why these children decided to end up schooling.

4. Summarize each interview, validate and modify. The conversation partners were given a copy of the themes together with the cluster of relevant meaning which corresponds to their interview. They were made to check whether the essence of their statements during the interview had been accurately described. Since all the respondents validated the truthfulness of the arrived reasons attributed to their underachievement in algebra, no modifications were made, and the themes were carried as the result of this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Conversation with "Jay" coded as "CPI"

He is 12 years old, and the second from the eldest among four siblings. His father died when he was 8 years old. A few years after the death of his father, his mother married again leaving them in his grandmother together with his two younger brothers. His eldest brother sometimes stays with them, and sometimes left them just to go to other places to earn for a living. He and his brothers had grown up on the custody of his grandmother. Most of the time he is in charge in doing daily household chores. They belong to a very low socio-economic status. Working in the farm is their primary source of living. He used to earn Php 100.00 a

day at the farm. All of them sometimes must work together to earn. His grandmother is already 70 years old, whom he pitied much because until now, she still works in the farm for them to survive.

Most of the time they experienced having nothing to eat at home. According to him, sometimes he needs to work alone for them to have something to eat for the day. Having with them some domesticated animals is an assurance for them to survive. Jay serves as a father and a brother to his family. He needs to work for them to survive. With regards to education, he considered it important, he values education as an essential element for him to be better, much in earning a better job. He is a good pupil, according to one of his teacher and his academic performance from previous years were average. The only thing is, his attendance at school is not constant. He decided to quit from schooling second quarter of school year 2017-2018. According to him, as much as he wanted to go to school, his responsibilities to provide their necessities at home is much more important. After his work at the farm, he felt so tired going to school. He must work specially during harvest and planting season. Helping his grandmother causes him to decide to withdraw from schooling. Another reason is the distance of the school from their home which is very far. He needs to walk miles before he reaches school, worst during rainy season.

Conversation with "Michael" coded as "CP2"

He is 11 years old and the second to the eldest of 5 siblings. On the other hand, he is the eldest son. He was in grade four when he decided to withdraw from school. Tracking up his records from grade one to four, he seems to have a low academic performance. Both of his parents did not able to finished elementary. Their major source of income is farming and therefore it is unstable. Basically, his parents can only provide an average and sometimes less of their needs as a child. Their parents on the other hand were eager to send them to school but not to the extent that they can really provide what their children need. Michael is much affected since he is the eldest son, he caters all the obligations and responsibilities next to his father. He used to do jobs which are not suited at his age. He is the right hand of his father in the family. At his age, his experience is much far and intense compare to a normal child.

He experienced having nothing to eat at home. He loves going to school. According to him, school is the only place where he can experience childhood activity. He can play, talk and laugh with his classmates and playmates. However, at the end of the day, his

obligations and responsibilities at home awaits. His tasks at home weighs more than his tasks at school. In fact, much of his time during weekend are spent in the farm than to study. He must help his family, or else, they will end up hungry. He used to take care of their raised animals, and looking foods for them is part of it. He also performs household chores such as cooking, washing clothes and securing water for the family. In addition, he also helps his parents working at their own farm and sometimes in others just to earn extra income. When he was in school, sometimes he experience being bullied by his classmates but much to his memory are good experiences. He is not an achiever, and according to him, his academic grades are low, but he still loves going to school. He believes that education can help him uplift his life better. On his interview why he ended up schooling, one day, he got ill, and it last for many days or almost a week. Gaining his strength again, he felt timid going to school thinking that his teacher will get mad at him, he also hears rumors that his teacher had already erased his name. Since then, he lost interest in going to school and prefer to stay at home doing his tasks and obligations.

Conversation with "John" coded as "CP3"

He is now 14 years old and the eldest child with one sister. He lives with both of his parents whose source of living is the same with the other respondents, they are farmers. He finds his life difficult because of their situation, they earn just for survival. As a son, he had to go with his parents at work. He had no choice but to help them just to provide their necessities. His parents, both did not able to go to school even in kinder and grade one. John abandoned school grade four at this present school year. According to him, he is so dull, at his grade level, he does not know how to read. True, since the researcher was able to let him try to do so. He can only name letters and sometimes even forget it. His teacher will always scold at him, but he can do nothing for it. He does not have any wore or worst experiences at school prior to his abandonment. He loves schooling despite of his difficulties in learning but much to his disappointment when his teacher asks him to submit his credentials specifically his birth certificate. When he asks his parents about it, the answer would always be "*I don't know*". Now, he is working at the farm and earning Php 100.00 a day. He finds it useful working at the farm, since he was able to give something for the family than going to school and earn nothing. He used to raise domesticated animals such as carabaos, chickens, goats, and fattened swine. When asked, if he still loves to go to school, his response was positive, but

he said he must have the necessary requirements and he should learn how to read and write.

Conversation with "Von" coded as "CP4"

He is 14 years old and the third from the eldest of 5 siblings. Though he is not the eldest son, but he need to help his family to survive. His eldest brother for him seemed to be so irresponsible. At home, he used to do household chores such cooking, washing dishes, taking care of their raised animals and securing food for them, look for fire woods and water. His mother would also ask him to take care of his youngest sister. He is much exposed to different works. Though his parents want them to go to school, he himself sometimes find it difficult to do both school works and household chores.

Their source of income primarily based on their work at the farm. The same with the previous respondents, rain or shine they must work to earn for living. He abandoned school grade four of the previous school year, according to him, as much as he forces himself to love schooling, he did not like it and he did not know why. Much to his discouragement when he encounters a strict teacher, especially because his classroom performance is poor. Another reason was the distance of their residence from school. Going to school is so tiring according to him, especially when he thinks of the works awaits at home when he arrived. He also has the concept on the importance of education in preparing for the future, however, his attitude towards schooling hinders him to go back.

The general responses of the respondents are coded and reflected as units of General Meanings.

After a rigorous data explication of the interviews conducted, seven essential themes emerged namely: a)child work; b)child labor; c)relevance of education to life d)parents financial stability and literacy; e)malnutrition; f)lack of interest or motivation; and g) school related problems.

The lived experiences of drop-out children as reflected on the clusters of relevant meanings by which the themes were drawn are the identified reasons attributed on the phenomena of dropping out by the children who participated on this study.

Parents financial instability and literacy is supported by scholars who stressed the importance of parental income, either without clear specifications (e.g. Dorn, 1996; Blue and Cook, 2004; Ishitani & Snider, 2006; Ou & Reynolds, 2006; Cataldi et al.,2009); or only in case parents' income is below the poverty line (Orthner et al., 2002); or when low family income is combined with structural aspects such as family disruption (Suet-Ling, 2000).

Further, it has been confirmed that there is a strong connection between the family environment and the rate

of school dropout: the family-related factors (standards of living, parent-child relationship, models of parenting) represent the main causes for school dropout; school dropout rate is highest in the poorer families; parents' lack of interest and lack of supervision of teenage children can result in their abandoning school; the low standards of living, as well as school dropout are due to the same factors: low income, low educational abilities of the parents, no workplace, excessive consumption of alcohol, divorce (Chirtes, 2010).

On the other hand, reasons attributed on the phenomena of pupils dropping out such as child work, child labor, poor nutrition, and lack of interest and motivation are strengthened by the findings of Adu-Yeboah (2010) that factors contributing to school drop-out and evident on other studies are: Child labor; Poverty; Teacher absenteeism; Irregular school attendance; Poor academic performance; Grade repetition; Corporal punishment; and Family shock (e.g. death of a parent). Moreover, he stated that drop out is a process, not an event; a combination of at-risk preceding factors make dropout easy.

School related problems is supported by the study of Davis and Rimm(1998) and as cited by Gallagher (2005) that within the school environment, there are several factors that may contribute to patterns of underachievement. Some of the factors that they have identified were unwelcoming school climate and inflexibility. Further, according to Karaduman (2013), the school is the place where most underachievement becomes visible.

The seven essential themes are made up of 19 clusters of relevant meaning. There are clusters common to all pupils, common to three of them, common to two of them, and unique clusters. The clusters of relevant meaning common to all include: Doing daily household chores and safekeeping of raised animals; time constraint in doing the task; early exposure to work; working for extra compensation; scarcity of food supply, importance of education and helping parents or guardian at work.

Clusters such as distant school from residency; tiredness after working; absence of electric power supply were shared by three of the respondents. Two of the conversation partners shared experiences related to illness.

Cluster of relevant meaning such as the absence of parents is distinct cluster on the first respondent, bullying is distinct on the second respondent.

Poor academic performance, school admission requirements, parents educational background and financial problem are clusters distinct to the third respondents while strict teacher is a unique experience of the fourth respondents.

Below is a thorough discussion of the experiences of the students on different reasons attributed to phenomena of dropping out that have been mentioned.

Theme 1: Child work

“Child work” refers to a positive participation of children in an economic activity, which is not detrimental to their health or mental and physical development; on the contrary, it is a beneficial work, which strengthens or encourages the child development. Findings of this study reveals that all of the respondents have lots of obligations at home. They were exposed to works specially in doing household chores and safekeeping of the animals. These responsibilities must be accomplished as means of helping their parents. However, due to number of obligations, respondents encounters time constraint in doing the tasks which in return hinders their eagerness to be in school. The following are their statements:

Pupil 1.

Sa buntag sir kay magkabo og magtugway sa kanding nya inug ka hapon magkabo, maghipos sa kanding nya manguha ug pasaw sa baboy. Ka da alas 6 sa buntag mo mata nako, nya mamahaw dayon magsugod sa ubra. Sa hapon kay sugod ko og ubra mga alas 4:00. Mga 10 akoa edad nagsugod ko ani na mga ubra nya 12 naman ko ron sir. (Every morning, I fetch water and secure foods for our swine and goat. I woke up every 6:00 o clock in the morning then right after eating, I start working. In the afternoon I resume to work at 4: 00 o clock. I started with this kind of work when I was still 10 years old now, I am already 12)

Pupil 2.

Akong ubra kay manghugas, maglung ag, magkabo ug magbugha, manugway sa mga hayop na baka ug kabaw, magpakaon sa manok ug magpasaw sa baboy sir. Mga alas 7 sa buntag sugod nakog ubra ana nya balik inug ka hapon mga alas 3 sa hapon. Kung mahuman na nako tanan, mangguna mi sa baol. Mga usa na ko katuig ga sige ug ubra ani sir. (I used to wash dishes, cook rice, fetch water, secure fire-woods and

provide foods for our raised animals such as chicken, carabao and cow. I start working at 7:00 o clock in the morning and resume the same work at 3:00 o clock. If the tasks are done. We used to work in the farm. It is almost one year since I started doing these works.

Pupil 3.

Inug mata nako sa buntag mga alas singko sir manugway ko daan sa mga hayop usa ko maadto sa ako giubrahan, nya sa hapon magkuha sa mga gitugway na hayop nya maglatag pasaw sa baboy. Usahay sa hapon kung wala pa sila mama maglung ag ko daan. Mga 9 ako edad gasugod na ko sir, mga 5 na katuig kay 14 naman ko. (When I woke up at 5:00 o clock in the morning I secure and prepare foods for the animals before I started my work at the farm, in the afternoon I am in charge for the safekeeping of the animals. Sometimes when my parent is not yet around, I used to cook rice for dinner. I started doing these works when I was 9 years old and now I am 14 years old, so, Its almost 5 years.)

Pupil 4.

Kanang maglung ag, manugway sa kabaw ug kanding nya mangahoy, sahay magkabo. Sa hapon inug uli namo gikan ubra sa baol kay maglung-ag nya magkuha pod sa mga hayop. Mga alas 7 ko mo mata usahay ngitngit pa. Usahay pod dugay ko kamata kay lantaw mig tv sa among silingan maong dugay mi kamata. Dugay na sir uie, mga 10 o 11 ko gasugod og himo ani na mga ubra. Mga 3 na katuig kay 14 naman ko ron. Sayonan raman ko, Usahay kapuyan pod ko kay ako raman usa mag ubra nya upat naman kabuok among kabaw. Magbantay pa dyud diay ug bata sir kanang mo adto si mama sa meeting. Ang magdigamo ug magbantay sa bata mao gyoy importante kaayo. (Cooking rice, securing foods for animals, look for fire-woods and sometimes I fetch water. In the afternoon after our work in the farm, I used to cook rice for dinner and in charge for the safekeeping of the animals. Sometimes I woke up at 7: 00 o clock in the morning, sometimes earlier and sometimes I woke up late because we used to watch TV at our neighbor the previous night. It's been so long since I started doing this works. I was 10 or 11 that time and now I am 14. Its almost 3 years. I find it easy but sometimes I find it difficult specially if I am working alone, it is even now that we have 4 carabaos to be cared off. Sometimes I am also assigned to look after my baby sister when my mother has to attend meeting. Cooking rice and looking after my baby sister is the most important.

Theme 2: Child Labor

Child labor refers to the employment of children in any work that deprives children of their childhood, interferes with their ability to attend regular school, and that is mentally, physically, socially or morally dangerous and harmful. Result of the interview showed that there are pupils who are exposed to child labor. In this theme clustered three respondents' experiences. They have responded that they experience working just to earn for living.

As one pupil utters:

Paubrahon man ko ug pang guna sa baol sir. Tag 100 ang adlaw nya ihatag nako ni lola para igasto sa pagkaon sa balay. Mao pod na usahay di nako ganahan mo skwela kay kapoy kaayo gikan sa ubra sir. (I was allowed to work in the farm. I receive 100 pesos salary and I gave it to my grandmother for daily compensation. That is why sometimes I lost interest in going to school because I am very much exhausted after work)

Another pupil shares:

Gaubra man ko sa hacienda sir. Wala ko gipugos ug pangubra pero akoy ganahan kay para naa pod koy kwarta. Tag 100 ang adlaw sir. Mohatag ko nilang mama, nya magbiling pod ko para nako. Kapoy inog kahuman og ubra sir oy, pero cge nalang(I am working at the sugarcane farm although my parents does not obliged me but I prefer to work so that I can earn money. I receive 100 pesos a day. I gave some of it to my mother and keep some for my personal expenses. It is very tiring after work, but it's okay anyway)

Likewise, one of them says:

Talagsa raman ko mangubra, di pirme kay suko si papa. Wala ko nagubra ug guna, kana rang ting ani, mamakyaw ug hakot sa humay. Kung walay nay ani kay motabang ko ni papa manghakot kawayan para ibaligya. (Seldom I worked because my father will get mad. When harvest season arrives, that's the time we can earn by helping my father in gathering rice stalks and grains. If harvest season ended, I used to help my father in gathering bamboos to be sold.

Further he says:

Lisod gyud kaayo sir atong gaeskwela pa ko kay hapon naman ko mauli sa balay nya samot na og mo cleaners pa gyod mi kay mahapnan na ko og maayo nya daghan pa kaayo ulubrahon sa balay (It is very difficult for me specially when I was still studying because I use to go home late in the afternoon. It is harder when we are assigned to clean the classroom, because I will

arrive home very late and there are plenty of work to be done)

Theme 3: Relevance of Education to Life

Findings of the study also revealed that children themselves know the importance of education in their life. They had inculcated in their minds that acquiring quality education could lead them to have an easy life.

One of them clearly speaks:

Importante gyod ang maka eskwela sir oy para makakita kag nindot na trabaho sa ulihi. (Being educated is very important, so that in the end, you can have a better job).

And the rest of the conversation partners utters the same responses as to the relevance of education to life.

Theme 4: Parents Financial Instability and Literacy

Parents financial instability. Results on the conversation with the respondents also shows that children experienced problems related to financial aspects of their parents.

One of the pupils stresses:

Kana pod usahay na wala mi inug bayad sa alamutan kay di man mi member sa 4 P's sir. Di dyod kabayad sa bayranan sa skuylahan si mama diri kay daghan man mi ug utang gud. Mas ok gane kuno na ning undang ko kay makatabang ko nila. (There are instances that we cannot pay our school contribution. We are unable to pay because my mother has lots of debts. It is better for them that I decided to quit from schooling so that I can help them).

Further, all of the respondents addressed that they do not have access to electricity due to financial problem. As one of them relays:

Wala man mi kuryente sa balay sir. Mahal man pa connect. Among gamit kay suga ra na de gas. (We do not have access to electricity at home. We are using the traditional kerosene lamp).

In which the rest of the respondents stress the same. *Parents Literacy.* Two of the conversation partners put emphasis on their parents' educational background. One of the respondents clearly speaks:

Lisod kaayo ang dili ka eskwela sir oy pareho nilang mama ug papa. Wala man gyod na sila kaeskwela ug elementary. Dili gyod ka kakita ug nindot na ubra (Being uneducated is hard just like my parents, they did not even enter elementary. It would be hard for you to search for a better job)

Likewise, one of them says:

Si mama ug si papa gane sir wala man pod na sila kahuman og elementary. (Even my parents did not able to finished elementary).

On the other hand, one of the respondents stresses the absence of his parents. As he clearly states:

Patay naman akong papa sir, nya si mama namana pod og usab maong naa nalang ko sa ka lola ga puyoron kuyog akoang usa ka manghod. Naa naman pod lain pamilya si mama naa sa Talisay. (My father is deceased and my mother marries again that is why I am staying with my grandmother together with my younger sister. My mother has already a new family at Talisay City).

Theme 5: Malnutrition

Findings of this study disclosed that conversation partners experienced despair in terms of getting their basic needs. All of them have experienced food shortage which could lead to illness and resulted in having poor nutrition.

Scarcity of Food Supply. On Maslow's hierarchy of needs, the acquisition of physiological or basic needs must be attain first before the others. Hence, it clearly indicates the importance of food in daily living. In this study, the responses of the conversation partners clustered as one particularly in the scarcity of food supply. Here are some of their statements:

Respondent 1.

Makakaon raman mi pamahaw, paniudto ug panihapon sir. Pero mahutdan pod mi usahay ug bugas mga kausa sa usa ka simana. Manghulam ra mi sa amoang silingan. May laag makatabang ug sanggi kay naay ubay ubay na bugas. (we can have our breakfast, lunch and dinner but sometimes, we run out of food once every week. Lucky during harvest season since we can have plenty of food supply)

Respondent 2.

Makakaon raman mi katulo sa usa ka adlaw sir. Usahay mahutdan mi og bugas. Magkaon ra mi og mga salag on. Mangita raman pod paagi si mama para makakitag bugas. Maghagdaw ug mais o humay daun ibulad nya ipagaling. Mao pod bitaw ning undang ko sir kay usahay wala man mi kanoon (We can eat three times a day. Sometimes, we run out of rice. We just eat root crops. My mother will look for a remedy for us to have foods. We look for leftovers in corn or rice plantation. We let it dry from the sun and have it milled. This why I decided to quit from schooling because sometimes we have nothing to eat.

Respondent 3.

Makakaon raman mi katulo sa usa ka adlaw. Usahay kasulay mi na wa nay bugas sir, utan ra amo gikaon. manghulam rapod mi bugas sa amoang amo. (We can eat meals three times a day. There are times when we run out of rice and we just eat vegetable alone. We just borrow rice from our boss.

Respondent 4.

Makakaon raman mi katulo sa usa ka adlaw. Kasulay mi sir uie na wala mi panihapon mga sa usa kabulan kaduha katulo. (We can have our three meals in a day. Sometime, we experienced having no dinner seldom twice or thrice a month)

Illness. Two of the respondent responses that one of their reasons of quitting from school is having health problems.

One of them puts it this way:

Ning sugod kog undang sir tungod atong gihilantan ko ug usa ka simana. Nya pagbalik nako ug eskuyla giingnan man ko sa akoang mga classmates na gipala na ni maam ang akoang ngalan. Maulaw na pod ko maong wala nalang pod ko ning balik. (I started to quit when I got illness for one week. When I went back to school, my classmates told me that my teacher had already erased my name, so, I was ashamed and decided to stop

Another pupil says:

Ning undang ko sir katong naka absent ko og pila ka adlaw kay na ospital ko sir. Di na dayon ko ganahan mo balik sa eskuylahan pagkaayo nako. (I started to quit when I absent for several days because I was rushed to the hospital. But when I recovered, I never felt going back to school again.

Theme 6: Lack of Interest or Motivation

One of the significant findings of this study revealed that pupils lacked interest or motivation. Motivation is vital in keeping the children interested to perform beyond of what is expected from them. According to Chukwu-Etu (2009), one of the important reasons for pupils' underachievement in any academic area can be identified as insufficient motivation to apply actively the understanding they have.

Poor academic performance and Lack of interest in education. These are also reasons attributed to the phenomena. The study showed that there are really children who cannot reach at par along with the standards of what the teachers or institution had set. Moreover, having a poor self-motivation towards education is also evident. Children possesses stigma

that school is nothing, and they can earn nothing from it. The purpose of education is not clearly understood. Hence, it ends up having an easy decision of dropping out from school. This experience is common to two of the respondents.

One of them clearly speaks:

Kay kung mo eskuyla pod ko sir wa man pod koy makuha god. Perte gyod kong bogoa sir uie, dili gyod ko kablo mobasa. Mag ugtas nalang si sir nako madugay. Nya og mag praktis pod ko og basa sir magsakit madugay akong ulo maong mo undang nalang ko og basa. (If I go to school, I can earn nothing, I am so dull, I do not even know how to read. My teacher soon gets mad at me. And when I started practice reading, I got headache, so I had to stop reading)

The other one says:

Wala man koy gana mo skwela sir. Ambot nganong wala gyod koy gana mo skwela. Usahay mo ganahan ko usahay dili. Lisod man gud kaayo ang ipang klase sir nya daghan pod og ubra sa balay. (I do not have interest in schooling. I do not know why. Sometimes, I feel it and sometimes I don't. Our topics are so difficult and there are also lots of things to do at home)

Theme 7: School-Related Problems

Findings of the study likewise revealed that dropping out of children is attributed with factors related to school such as bullying, school admission requirements, strict teacher and distant school from residency.

School misfit refers to disparity between students' needs and the requirements of the school or between the students' potential and learning tasks. The authors (Schargel, 2001; Salvastru, 2004; Zidarescu, 2009; Marco, 2010) differentiate between the pedagogical misfit that refers to the incapacity of achieving the school tasks and the behavioral misfit associated to discipline and interaction issues regarding students or pupil inside the school environment. School misfit is fostered by a series of factors such as: school failures, incapacity of responding to the requirements of the school community, school immaturity (Cristea, 2000).

Balfanz and Legters (2004) have asserted that if a school has more "promoting power" (that is: an overall higher percentage of pupils passing timely from one grade to the following) – perhaps evidently – dropout is less. Thus, schools that are attended by minority students tend to have low promoting power, especially majority minority schools.

Bullying. Bullying is not just a problem in the society, but it is also present in every school. This study

showed that one of the respondents have a unique experienced of maltreatment of his colleagues at school. He clearly speaks:

Nag sumbagay man mi ato sa akoang classmate sir, nya nagpalaban sya sa iyahang mga kauban. Ga plano man sila na ilaha kong tabangan maong mahadlok nako mo balik sa eskuylahan. (My classmate and I had a quarrel, then he asks for help from his group. They all planned to go against me, I got scared and that's why I am afraid to go back to school).

School Admission Requirements. One of the requirements of the school for the pupils to be formally enrolled is their birth certificate, however, there are really pupils whose parents were unable to have them registered. Hence, it ends up to child's withdrawal from school. This is true to the experience of one of the respondents.

He described his experience as:

Ning undang ko sir kay gi pangitaan naman ko ni sir nako sa akoang birth certificate nya wala man gud mi naparehistro ni mama. Sigehan pod nako si mama ingon dili man sya kabalo unsaon (I quit from schooling because my teacher is asking about my birth certificate however, my mother did not have us registered. I keep on telling my mother about it but she said she doesn't know how)

Strict teacher. Teacher always play a vital role in pupils' development. This is supported by Heler (1992) and cited by Karaduman (2013) that the organization of teaching and personality of the teacher were two main factors that influenced the achievement of children in the classroom. One of the conversation partners asserted his experience about his teacher. He clearly speaks:

Mo eskwela ra man gyod tane ko sir. Galeng isog man pod kaayo amoang maestra gud. Istriktahon man si maam namo labi nag magpabuyag pa gyod mi. (I like to go back to school, but our teacher is so furious. Ma'am seem strict specially if all of us are naughty).

Distant School from Residence. One of the contributing factors on drop out incidence is the distance of the school from their home or residency. Some of the pupils really need to travel miles and had to cross rivers before they reach school. Usually, they do not feel going to school due to bad weather condition. And if they will, they are prone to encounter lots of hazards along the way. These experiences were shared by two of the conversation partners. One of them says:

Perting layoa jud sa amoa sir oy. Kapoy kaayo baklay patubang sa iskuylahan nya samot nag mag

ulan sir, kay perte na gyong lisura ang dalan. Usahay mo absent nalang ko. (Our home is very far. I always get tired of walking going to school. Worst when it rains because our way going to school is much more difficult. Sometime, I used to absent)

Further, another pupil responded:

Ang amoang balay sir kay layo man gud sa iskuylahan. Usahay udto na gyod ko maabot labi nag daghag ubra sa balay. Kapoy pod lagi kaayo baklay patubang sa skuylahan sir kay tungason man. (Our home is far from school. Sometimes i arrived at school late specially when there are lots of works at home. It is so tiring when walking going to school, the way is so steep.

CONCLUSION

The result indicates that pupils were not just pupils at school, but they are also workers at home. Although child works are consider good, however, too much of it causes burden to children. Likewise, it also reveals that until now, there are still children who are exposed to child labor. Although the government had implemented programs to render assistance and help for these children (such as 4P's), however, it does not compensate their needs as an individual.

Based on the narration of the pupils, all of them know the importance of education to their lives. However, due to several factors that arise, they find it more difficult to find its significance. Even if they pursue to attain and have a better and quality education but with the burdens they encounter at their early age, it could be a great contributing factors for them to decide to quit from schooling.

Malnutrition also sprung up since there is a scarcity of food supply. Our body needs essential nutrients in order to function normally. However, their body does not receive what is necessary. Thus, it leads to illness. On the other hand, the Department of Education implemented the School-Base Feeding Program to aid malnutrition, but due to latter reasons, children failed to go to school by which the program was implemented.

Moreover, pupils lack of interest or motivation is related to malnutrition and exposure to work. Pupils does not understand the essence of going to school since they have to think on what to do for them to survive rather than thinking of what to do for them to learn. Thus, they tends to have poor academic performance and started to lost interest in their study.

Likewise, one of the factors is the financial status of parents. We cannot deny the fact that almost all aspects of human lives involve money. In that sense, sending a

child to a school really requires financial support. And therefore parents with unstable financial support could lead to pupils abandoning school.

School related factors also arises based on the finding of the study. Every school sets its policies by which all of the stakeholders should abide particularly in the admission of the pupils. Pupils who failed to present their personal credentials will probably be not admitted. In as much as the pupils wants to be in school, but due to failure in presenting the required documents, they tend to develop disappointment and result to withdrawal. Likewise, distance of the school is also a factor by which pupils develop laziness towards schooling since they have to walk miles before reaching the school.

Another school related factor is the teacher. Teachers attitude and compassion are necessary in motivating children to develop interest towards schooling. In as much as every teacher wants every child to learn, they tend to implement discipline and actions which will probably be misinterpreted by the children. Children think it on a different way not parallel to what the teacher wanted him to understand. Thus, the child develops negative sense towards his teachers.

To sum it up, themes such as child labor, child work, parents financial instability and literacy and malnutrition resulted due to poverty. This encompasses a major part in the experiences of drop out children. On the other hand, drop out phenomena is also attributed with problems related to school. Hence, school must also acknowledge that partly, they have contributed to the phenomena. School and children should compliment with each other. As stated by Jardine (2003) the elementary schools seem to have figured out what their students needed. They, for the most part, provided a nurturing, supportive environment consistent with what students required at their developmental stage.

The aforementioned reasons hinders the belief of the pupils that education is very important to their lives. The process is a struggle for them and most of those pupils with the same experience will probably end up the same.

RECOMMENDATION

It would be that the school may identify and develop a program for at risk children so that they will not end up to withdrawal. There may be a intensive monitoring on the implementation of child labor policy. Government may also provide additional livelihood programs to uplifts the socio- economic status of poor

families. The school needs to have a caring and understanding environment to promote welfare and encouragement to pupils. If this can be balanced and accomplished, many pupils may be spared from difficulties that cause them to withdraw or leave schooling.

COPYRIGHTS

Copyright of this article is retained by the author/s, with first publication rights granted to JETM. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.)

REFERENCES

- Ampiah, J. G., & Adu-Yeboah, C. (2009). Mapping the incidence of school dropouts: a case study of communities in Northern Ghana. *Comparative Education, 45*(2), 219-232.
- Balfanz, R. and N. Legters (2005). Locating the Dropout Crisis. Which High Schools Produce the Nation's Dropouts? Where Are They Located? Who Attends Them? Center for Research on the Education of Students Placed at Risk (CRESPAR).
- Chirtes, G. (2010). A Case Study into the Causes of School Dropout. *Acta Didactica Napocensia, 3*(4), 25-34.
- Dekker, G. W., Pechenizkiy, M., & Vleeshouwers, J. M. (2009). Predicting Students Drop Out: A Case Study. *International Working Group on Educational Data Mining*.
- Eccles, J. S., Barber, B. L., Stone, M., & Hunt, J. (2003). Extracurricular activities and adolescent development. *Journal of social issues, 59*(4), 865-889.
- Journal of Social Issues, 59 (4), 865- 882. Hyunsan, C., Hallfors, D. D., & Sanchez, V. (2005). Evaluation of a High School Peer Group Intervention for At-Risk Youth. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology, 33* (3), 363-379.
- Kristof De Witte, Sofie Cabus, Geert Thyssen, Wim Groot, Henriette Maassen van den Brink, (2013), A Critical Review of the Literature on School Dropout.
- Miller, C. (2006). *Dropped Out or Pushed Out: A Case Study on Why Students Drop Out Graduate Degree Major: MS Guidance and Counseling Research Advisor: Amy Gillett Ph. D. Month~ Year December, 2006 Number of Pages: 53*(Doctoral dissertation, University of Wisconsin-Stout).
- Nowicki Jr. S., Duke, M.P., Sisney, S., Stricker, B., & Tyler, M. A. (2004). Reducing the Dropout Rates of At-Risk High School Students. The e\Effective Learning Program. *Genetic, Social and General Psychology Monographs, 130* (3), 225-239.
- Wilson, S.J. Tanner-Smith, E.E., Lipsey, M.W., Steinka-Fry, K. & Morrison, J. (2011). Dropout Prevention and Intervention Programs: Effects on School Completion and Dropout Among School-Aged Children and Youth. *Campbell Systematic Reviews 8*, DOI: 10.4073/csr.2011.8.